

Craniometrical sexual dimorphism of the grey wolf (*Canis lupus*, Canidae, Carnivora) in Bulgaria

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Abstract: Cranial sexual dimorphism in grey wolf (*Canis lupus* Linnaeus, 1758) from Bulgaria has not been studied so far. Skulls from adult individuals from across the country were studied. Thirty-six parameters (35 craniodental measurements and a volumetric one) of each skull were measured. The results showed that there was similar mean variability for all parameters in both sexes ($V_c = 6.1$ for males and $V_c = 6.6$ for females). The study presented the sexual size dimorphism in linear parameters of the skull as a male/female ratio and as a percentage (male-female)/female*100. The descriptive statistics of the obtained data revealed that the least variable parameters in both sexes were basal length, condylobasal length and cranial width. The most variable parameters of the wolf's skull in males and females were length of crista sagittalis externa, frontal breadth, maximal occipital breadth and rostrum width of the cranium and height of the ramus of the mandible (between P_4 - M_1). The least sex-dependent parameters were postorbital breadth, the least diameter of bulla tympanica, the greatest diameter of bulla tympanica and brain skull volume as a non-linear parameter. The mandibular width and greatest skull length are among the parameters that exhibit the most significant sexual dimorphism. Additionally, the width of the mandibular processus articularis and the mesiodistal C length also show sexual dimorphism. The Bulgarian wolf population exhibits weak craniodental sexual dimorphism, which is male-biased, as is typical in canids with a monogamous social system. However, the sexual dimorphism is more pronounced than in the studied more northern populations.

Keywords: canids, *Canis lupus*, cranium, male-biased, sexual dimorphism

Introduction

The grey wolf (*Canis lupus* Linnaeus, 1758) is a resident species in Bulgaria, with a fragmented distribution in Europe (Boitani et al., 2018). During the breeding season it mainly inhabits the mountains and partly the plains and hilly areas of Northeastern Bulgaria. It descends to the valleys during the autumn and until the middle of the winter (Popov & Sedefchev, 2003; Spassov, 2007; Spiridonov &

Spassov, 2011). The species is listed “vulnerable” in the Red Data Book of Bulgaria (Spiridonov & Spassov, 2011).

Sexual dimorphism in species is primarily driven by the sexual selection (Erlinge, 1979; Gittleman & Van Valkenburgh, 1997). However, it is geographically dependent and influenced by local selective forces (Connallon, 2015). In some species, such as grey wolf, sexual dimorphism may depend on the segregation of the trophic niches of the two sexes (Ko-

Fig. 1. Location (red circles) and number of shot wolves, respectively the obtained skulls, measured in the present study. The map does not include some of the skulls from the National Museum of Natural History's collection due to unknown origin.

rablev et al., 2021). On the Balkans and in Bulgaria, its sexual dimorphism has been investigated based on body parameters only (Trbojević & Ćirović, 2016; Tsingarska et al., 2019), but the cranial sexual size dimorphism has not yet been studied. The present study aimed to investigate and determine the sexual size dimorphism in some cranial features of the grey wolf in Bulgaria.

The features of the mammalian cranium are informative and serve as a proper tool for understanding adaptive evolutionary processes (Machado, 2020) and are systematically significant (Simpson, 1945; Tryon, 1951; Novacek, 1993; McKenna & Bell, 1997; Kemp, 2005).

Material and methods

The collected skulls were divided into two age classes – juveniles (under 1 year of age) and adults (over 1 year of age). The juveniles were excluded from the

present study because of their uncompleted growth. The age of the skulls was determined using a combination of methods, including tooth eruption and degree of incisor's wear (Fuller & Keith, 1980; Gipson et al., 2000), as well as ossification of synchondrosis intersphenoidalis and synchondrosis sphenoccipitalis (Landon et al., 1998). The method of determining age by cementum annulus counts on a canine tooth section considered the most accurate method (Goodwin & Ballard, 1985) was not applied for assessing the age of skulls due to their trophy value.

For this study, cranial material from 121 wolves (*Canis lupus* Linnaeus, 1758) over one year (54 males and 67 females) from the whole territory of Bulgaria (Fig. 1) was measured. The main part of the skulls (85 adult specimens) is stored in the National Museum of Natural History at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia. Most of these skulls are from animals hunted around the middle of the last century. Fifteen skulls, provided by hunters and forestry staff for 2 au-

Fig. 2. Most of the measured craniodental parameters of the Bulgarian grey wolf. A – left lateral view; B – dorsal view; C – ventral view; D – left lateral view of the mandible.

tumn-winter hunting seasons – from 2021 to 2023, were processed in the Taxidermy laboratory at the Faculty of Agriculture, Trakia University, Stara Zagora. An additional 21 adult specimens were obtained from private trophy collection.

Thirty-six parameters (35 linear and 1 volumetric) of each skull were measured through mechanical calliper with an accuracy of 0.01mm and shown in Appendix: Table 1. Most of the measurements followed

von den Driesch (1976) and are marked as such. The rest measurements were according to Onar et al. (2005), Milenković et al. (2006) and Loy et al. (2008).

Most of the parameters are shown on Fig. 2. The sexual dimorphism in linear parameters of the skull was presented as a standard male/female ratio and as a percentage (male-female)/female*100 (Hillis & Mallory, 1996; Mulders, 1997; Koroblev et al., 2020). Univariate descriptive statistics and linear regression

Fig. 3. Box plot for: A – mandibular width (at M1); B – greatest skull length; C – mandibular processus articularis; D – mesiodistal length of the upper canine of adult *C. lupus* skulls from Bulgaria.

statistical analyses were performed by IBM SPSS Statistics ver.26.

Results and discussion

Descriptive statistics of the data showed that the least variable parameters in both sexes were BL, CBL and CW (Appendix: Tables 2–3). The greatest skull length had a slightly higher variability in both sexes probably due to individual differences in the growth rate of the occipital crest, which was taken as a base point for this measurement. Otherwise, CBL and BL were of approximately equally low variability in both sexes. Zygomatic width is the main indicator in any craniometric study and in our case, it again had an average variability in both sexes ($V_c = 7.87$ for males and $V_c = 7.36$ for females). The most variable

parameters of the wolf skull in males were CSEL, FB, maxOCB and RW of the cranium and RH of the mandible, and in females – CSEL, FB, IoB, RW, maxOCB and again RH.

In both males and females, tooth row parameters showed low variability, with males ranging from 3.14 for LTRL to 5.11 for UTRL, and females ranging from 4.06 for UCtRL to 5.95 for UTRL. Compared to other cranial parameters, the variability was weak to moderate. In both sexes UTRL had the highest variability among tooth rows. Carnassial teeth length showed similar variability in both sexes, with males having values of V_c for $LP_4 - 4.5$ and $LM_1 - 5.23$ and females having values of V_c for $LP_4 - 4.69$ $LM_1 - 4.59$. These results contradict the claim of Dayan (2002) that dental features in carnivore populations are more variable than cranial ones and confirm the findings of Korablev et al. (2021).

Fig. 4. Relationship between condylobasal length and zygomatic width in male and female grey wolves from Bulgaria.

The cranial cavity volume varied significantly between males and females, with values of $V_c - 7.75$ and $V_c - 9.85$, respectively (Appendix: Tables 2–3).

The mean variability for all parameters was similar in both sexes ($V_c = 6.1$ for males and $V_c = 6.6$ for females). However, while Okarma & Buchalczyk (1993) reported greater variability for males from Bialowieża Primeval Forest (north-eastern Poland) and from Carpathian Mts (south-eastern Poland). In contrast, Hell & Paule (1982) found higher variability in females from Slovakian Carpathian Mts. The data aligns with Korablev et al. (2021), that the coefficient of variation, which expresses the variability of craniological features, is equal in both sexes. However, it is important to note that any subjective evaluations have been excluded. The variability observed is likely due to the characteristics of the local populations in different geographical areas, once the ratio of the sample size by sex in the different studies mentioned above is excluded.

Male-biased sexual dimorphism was found in all cranial parameters, ranging from 3.02% for CW to 12.08% for CSEL. Similarly, all the mandibular parameters also showed sexual dimorphism in favour of males, ranging from 4.41% for LCtRL to 10.42%

for $MW(M_1)$. The difference in mandibular width, was strongly determined by sex ($R^2 = 0.438$) (see also Fig. 3A). The parameter that showed the most significant sexual dimorphism was also the greatest skull length (Fig. 3B), the width of the mandibular processus articularis (Fig. 3C) and the mesiodistal C length (Fig. 3D). These results are consistent with previous studies, that have shown the same tendency (Gittleman & Van Valkenburgh, 1997; Larther et al., 2012; Chikachev et al., 2017; Korablev et al., 2020).

Maxillary and mandibular tooth row lengths showed minimal sexual dimorphism, ranging from 4.41% to 5.68% (Appendix: Table 4). Parameters describing the size of the carnassial teeth, along with the height of the upper canine tooth, exhibited a similar trend. The limited sex differences in carnassial teeth (P_4 and M_1) could be a result of the similar efforts while feeding. These teeth are used primarily for bone breaking and tissue shearing (Severtsov et al., 2016).

Over half of the linear skull features varied by only 5–7%. The least dependent on sex were PoB ($R^2 = 0.05$), LBTD ($R^2 = 0.06$) and GBTD ($R^2 = 0.08$).

The cranial cavity volume showed a sexual dimorphism of 4.84% in favour of the males which

value was lower than the average for all linear morphological features studied. Brain volume is considered closely linked to social behaviour, learning and behavioural plasticity (Sol et al., 2008; Benson-Amram et al., 2016). This parameter was also found to be not dependent on sex ($R^2 = 0.07$).

The study revealed that the average value of sexual size dimorphism in wolves from Bulgaria was 6.76%, which is approximately twice that of wolves in Central Russia – 3.55% (Korablev et al., 2021). Sexual selection, particularly male competition during mating season, generally explains the nature of such dimorphism. (Erlinge, 1979; Gittleman & Van Valkenburgh, 1997; Morris & Brandt, 2014; Korablev et al., 2021). The study suggests that the difference in the diet of male and female is influenced also by their different specialisations. Males tend to specialise in killing large ungulates, while females specialise in nursing during the pup-rearing period. This is related to the segregation of the trophic niches of both sexes, as noted in previous studies (Hillis & Mallory, 1996; Korablev et al., 2021). In a related species such as the African black-backed jackal (*Canis mesomelas*), sexual dimorphism depends on whether it lives in allopatry or in sympatry with other related species. Macdonald et al. (2004) found that sexual dimorphism of metric cranial parameters is enhanced in allopatric populations. It is possible that the higher sexual dimorphism observed in our study is due to the lack of strong taxonomically and size-similar competitors for the wolf in Bulgaria, unlike those from the rest of the Palaearctic.

Following Larter et al. (2012) we tested the correlation between the most frequently used external parameters of the skull – CBL and ZW in male and female grey wolves. The results obtained showed the same positive linear relationship between these parameters in both, males and females (Fig.4).

Conclusion

The present study fills the gap in the knowledge on the sexual dimorphism in metric skull parameters of grey wolf from Bulgaria and the Balkans. The species exhibits weak and male-biased craniodental sexual dimorphism, like all the canids with a typical monogamous social system (Gittleman & Van Valkenburgh 1997; Bidau & Martinez 2016). However, it is more pronounced than the sexual

dimorphism studied in several more northern wolf forest populations in Europe. The mandibular width and the greatest skull length are among the parameters that showed the most significant sexual dimorphism. Additionally, the width of the mandibular processus articularis and the mesiodistal C length also showed significant sexual dimorphism. The sex-separated biometric analyses from the present study will support further studies on geographic dimorphism in different grey wolf populations.

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Appendix

Table 1. Measurements and their abbreviations.

UPPER CRANIUM	GL*	greatest length
	CBL*	condylobasal length
	BL*	basal length
	CL*	cranial length
	GNL*	greatest nasal length
	LNL	least nasal length
	CSEL*	length of crista sagittalis externa
	ZW*	zygomatic width
	CAB*	breadth at the dental alveoli of maxillary canine teeth
	RW	rostrum width
	IFB	infraorbital breadth
	IoB*	interorbital breadth
	FB*	frontal breadth
	PoB*	postorbital breadth
	CW*	cranium width
	maxOCB	maximal occipital breadth
	GBTD*	the greatest diameter of bulla tympanica
	LBTD	the least diameter of bulla tympanica
	LP ₁	length of P ₄ of the upper jaw
	UCH	upper canine height
	GPB	greatest palatine breadth
	LP ₂ -M ₂	length from P ₂ to M ₂ included
	UCtRL	length of the upper cheek tooth row (P ₁ -M ₂)
	UTRL	length of the upper tooth row (C-M ₂)
SH*	skull height	
BSV	brain skull volume	
MANDIBLE	MDLC	mesiodistal length of upper canine
	APML*	length of the mandible from I ₁ dental alveoli to the angular process (proc. angularis)
	CPML	length of the mandible from the I ₁ dental alveoli to the condylar process (proc. condylaris)
	LM ₁	length of M ₁ of the mandible
	MW	mandibular width (at M ₁)
	RH	height of the ramus of the mandible (between P ₄ -M ₁)
	AP-CP*	distance between angular and condylar process of the mandible
	LTRL	length of the lower tooth row (C-M ₃)
	LCtRL*	length of the cheek tooth row (P ₁ -M ₃)
	WPA	width of processus articularis of the mandible

* taken from Von den Driesch (1976).

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of morphometric data for male grey wolf (*Canis lupus*) skulls from Bulgaria.

parameter	N	Mean	Min	Max	SD	Vc
GL	54	251.32	221.20	277.80	11.57	4.61
CBL	52	234.70	200.04	256.20	9.40	4.01
BL	53	221.62	196.00	242.70	8.39	3.79
CL	54	134.75	116.30	152.10	7.61	5.65
GNL	54	93.40	78.50	106.10	5.68	6.08
LNL	54	82.22	69.80	93.15	4.78	5.82
CSEL	54	83.45	59.50	107.90	12.65	15.15
ZW	54	137.54	114.50	170.70	9.79	7.12
CAB	53	46.75	42.52	51.20	2.03	4.34
RW	54	42.48	38.00	59.40	3.34	7.87
IFB	54	50.77	46.15	55.29	2.23	4.40
IoB	54	45.46	37.20	54.20	3.70	8.14
FB	54	62.41	48.00	72.50	5.78	9.26
PoB	54	42.23	35.70	48.70	2.92	6.91
CW	54	71.45	63.95	76.60	2.95	4.13
maxOCB	52	49.80	43.00	66.65	4.60	9.23
GBTD	54	29.38	25.40	32.30	1.64	5.58
LBTD	54	21.98	18.10	24.60	1.86	8.47
P ₄ L	54	23.90	21.70	26.53	1.08	4.50
MDLC	52	15.21	12.50	17.50	0.97	6.38
UCH	51	31.04	18.30	35.50	3.04	9.78
GPB	54	62.81	57.30	68.90	2.45	3.91
P ₂ M ₂ L	54	73.52	61.48	79.40	2.87	3.91
UCtRL	54	83.60	76.41	90.77	2.62	3.14
UTRL	54	103.35	93.35	133.90	5.28	5.11
SH	53	76.55	65.10	91.40	4.63	6.05
BSV	53	151.17	124.00	177.00	11.72	7.75
APML	54	185.07	163.20	206.50	8.57	4.63
CPML	54	185.06	161.20	208.00	7.92	4.28
M ₁ L	54	26.95	23.90	29.80	1.41	5.23
MW(M ₁)	54	14.34	12.50	16.10	0.74	5.16
RH (P ₄ -M ₁)	54	29.44	23.90	33.70	2.35	7.98
AP-CP	54	77.45	61.90	86.10	5.76	7.44
WPA	52	32.94	28.00	38.50	2.41	7.31
LTRL	53	117.17	104.86	123.09	3.68	3.14
LCtRL	52	94.36	85.20	101.70	3.28	3.48

Craniometrical sexual dimorphism of the grey wolf (*Canis lupus*, Canidae, Carnivora) in Bulgaria

Table 3. Descriptive statistics of morphometric data for female grey wolf (*Canis lupus*) skulls from Bulgaria.

parameter	N	Mean	Min	Max	SD	Vc
GL	67	234.61	210.20	256.80	11.14	4.75
CBL	64	221.29	192.80	241.30	9.21	4.16
BL	66	209.72	182.10	227.60	9.21	4.39
CL	67	126.95	111.50	144.00	7.30	5.75
GNL	66	86.50	70.30	99.20	6.02	6.96
LNL	66	76.15	62.40	86.60	5.02	6.59
CSEL	67	74.46	54.40	102.10	9.98	13.40
ZW	67	128.32	106.30	151.50	9.44	7.36
CAB	64	43.30	37.10	52.10	2.70	6.23
RW	67	39.43	31.50	49.00	3.53	8.95
IFB	67	47.76	39.80	56.00	3.41	7.14
IoB	67	41.99	33.40	51.00	3.82	9.10
FB	67	57.99	45.10	73.80	6.34	10.94
PoB	67	40.92	34.80	47.30	2.65	6.47
CW	67	69.35	62.42	74.70	2.81	4.05
maxOCB	65	46.56	41.60	62.30	3.77	8.09
GBTD	67	28.33	22.50	32.00	1.95	6.88
LBTD	67	21.11	16.90	25.50	1.64	7.77
P ₄ L	67	22.54	19.70	24.82	1.06	4.69
MDLC	42	13.82	11.60	17.00	0.99	7.18
UCH	64	28.60	21.30	35.80	2.35	8.21
GPB	67	59.53	51.20	67.50	2.86	4.80
P ₂ M ₂ L	67	70.41	59.30	78.40	3.07	4.35
UCtRL	67	80.00	70.20	88.30	3.25	4.06
UTRL	67	98.18	87.70	123.60	5.85	5.95
SH	67	71.18	47.30	79.60	4.85	6.81
BSV	65	144.18	96.00	175.00	14.20	9.85
APML	67	173.71	153.10	191.30	8.29	4.77
CPML	67	173.46	153.80	189.30	8.07	4.65
M ₁ L	67	25.37	22.30	27.50	1.17	4.59
MW(M ₁)	67	12.99	11.60	14.90	0.79	6.08
RH (P ₄ -M ₁)	67	26.94	21.40	30.76	2.20	8.15
AP-CP	67	71.05	58.60	81.70	5.53	7.78
WPA	42	30.16	25.30	35.30	2.36	7.82
LTRL	64	110.86	98.80	119.80	4.69	4.23
LCtRL	64	90.37	79.50	98.20	4.04	4.47

Table 4. Sexual size dimorphism in craniometric features of grey wolf (*Canis lupus*) from Bulgaria.

parameter	Mean/male	Mean/female	p	male/female ratio	SSD, %	R square
GL	251.32	234.61	0.000	1.07	7.12	0.35
CBL	234.70	221.29	0.000	1.06	6.06	0.34
BL	221.62	209.72	0.000	1.06	5.67	0.31
CL	134.75	126.95	0.000	1.06	6.15	0.22
GNL	93.40	86.50	0.000	1.08	7.98	0.26
LNL	82.22	76.15	0.000	1.08	7.97	0.28
CSEL	83.45	74.46	0.000	1.12	12.08	0.14
ZW	137.54	128.32	0.000	1.07	7.18	0.19
CAB	46.75	43.30	0.000	1.08	7.97	0.34
RW	42.48	39.43	0.000	1.08	7.73	0.16
IFB	50.77	47.76	0.000	1.06	6.30	0.21
IoB	45.46	41.99	0.000	1.08	8.26	0.18
FB	62.41	57.99	0.000	1.08	7.62	0.12
PoB	42.23	40.92	0.011	1.03	3.21	0.05
CW	71.45	69.35	0.000	1.03	3.02	0.12
maxOCB	49.80	46.56	0.000	1.07	6.94	0.13
GBTD	29.38	28.33	0.002	1.04	3.70	0.08
LBTD	21.98	21.11	0.007	1.04	4.12	0.06
P ₄ L	23.90	22.54	0.000	1.06	6.00	0.29
MDLC	15.21	13.82	0.000	1.10	10.10	0.34
UCH	31.04	28.60	0.000	1.09	8.53	0.17
GPB	62.81	59.53	0.000	1.06	5.52	0.27
P ₂ M ₂ L	73.52	70.41	0.000	1.04	4.42	0.22
UCtRL	83.60	80.00	0.000	1.04	4.49	0.27
UTRL	103.35	98.18	0.000	1.05	5.27	0.18
SH	76.55	71.18	0.000	1.08	7.53	0.24
BSV	151.17	144.18	0.005	1.05	4.84	0.07
APML	185.07	173.71	0.000	1.07	6.54	0.31
CPML	185.06	173.46	0.000	1.07	6.69	0.35
M ₁ L	26.95	25.37	0.000	1.06	6.22	0.28
MW(M ₁)	14.34	12.99	0.000	1.10	10.42	0.44
RH (P ₄ -M ₁)	29.44	26.94	0.000	1.09	9.27	0.23
AP-CP	77.45	71.05	0.000	1.09	9.01	0.25
WPA	32.94	30.16	0.000	1.09	9.20	0.26
LTRL	117.17	110.86	0.000	1.06	5.68	0.36
LCtRL	94.36	90.37	0.000	1.04	4.41	0.22